

CALENDAR
OF PAPERS RELATING TO
NEW SWEDEN

Classified under:

757 Riksarkivets ämnessamlingar. Miscellanea	757 Swedish National Archives subject collections. Miscellanea
16 Handel och sjöfart 1500 – 1800	16 Trade and maritime 1500 – 1800
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1636–1693

1. PETER LINDESTRÖM'S DESCRIPTION OF THE SOUTH
RIVER (DELAWARE) LOCATED IN NEW SWEDEN

From the farthest extent, at the territory of the Sanhickans¹, down the river to the Schuylkill, is 10 miles² of unused land bought from the Indians on condition that we may occupy and cultivate as much of it as we wish. These 10 miles of land are located on the west side of the river and remain in daily use by the Indians. It is estimated that this very beautiful land has a value of 2,000 Rijksdaalders per mile, totaling 20,000.

The Fort of Korsholm, situated in the mouth of the Schuylkill, along with the land located nearby, consists of 8 morgens³ of cultivated fields; the rest is unused but cultivable, together valued at 2,000 Rijksdaalders. Kingsessing, also called Vasa, is located half a mile upstream and is inhabited by around 20 free farmers, with approximately 20 morgens of cultivated farmland, well-stocked with livestock, estimated at 6,000 Rijksdaalders. Aronameck, located a quarter mile from here, includes approximately 4 morgens of cultivated farmland, valued at 500 Rijksdaalders.

The water mill at Möndall is estimated at 1,000 Rijksdaalders and the adjacent cultivated farmland of 4 morgens at 500 Rijksdaalders. Tinnakonk⁴, also known as New Gothenburg, has 50 head of livestock and 12 morgens of cultivated farmland. Belonging to Governor Printz, it is well-maintained and estimated at 4,000 Rijksdaalders. Tequirassy⁵, located a quarter mile downstream, includes 3 plantations and 12 morgens of cultivated farmland, estimated at 1,500 Rijksdaalders. All are stocked with livestock.

Upland, also called Mechkopenacka, consists of 12 morgens of cleared farmland with a house, estimated at 1,500 Rijksdaalders. Prinztorp, the property of Governor Printz, contains a brewery and 10 morgens of clear farmland, valued at 2,000 Rijksdaalders.

¹ A Lenape group who lived around present-day Trenton, New Jersey.

² The Dutch *mijl* although not even standardised within the Netherlands, was roughly 5 kilometers and is likely referred to here. A Swedish *mil* (today 10 kilometers) was set by the Swedish state in 1648 at 10.6 kilometers.

³ A unit of area used in the Netherlands, its extent varying by region but generally 8 to 10 km².

⁴ Tinicum Island, Pennsylvania.

⁵ The area at the mouth of Ridley Creek, a tributary of the Delaware.

Total value: 35,000 Rijksdaalders

Next are four plantations above Prinztorp, with breweries and stocked with livestock. The farmland consists of 16 morgens, valued at 2,000 Rijksdaalders. Fort Christina with buildings is valued at 10,000 Rijksdaalders. There are 16 morgens of cleared farmland just downstream, valued at 2,000 Rijksdaalders and a plantation further along the creek with 8 morgens of cleared farmland, valued at 1,000 Rijksdaalders.

Sandhook, where Fort Trinity⁶ is built, is valued at 8,000 Rijksdaalders. The land below it, being 20 morgens of cleared farmland, is valued at 1,500 Rijksdaalders, not including 20 houses. The cultivated land on the west side of the river, measured from the aforementioned Sandhook to Cape Henlopen, is about 16 miles of mostly clear land previously inhabited by the Indians. This area is valued at 32,000 Rijksdaalders.

The east side of the South River, from Cape May to the Fort Elfsborg, a distance of 14 miles, is uninhabited and valued at 28,000 Rijksdaalders. Elfsborg itself, with an adjoining 30 morgens of cleared land that has been planted by the English, is valued at 5,000 Rijksdaalders. The nine miles from Elfsborg upstream along the east bank is valued at 16,000 Rijksdaalders. The remaining land upstream to Sanhickan has not yet been purchased by us, except for two islands in the river, valued at 4,000 Rijksdaalders.

Total value of lands: 144,500 Rijksdaalders.

Vol. 196, ff.6r-13r.
1654. Swedish.

2. THE ENGINEER PETER LINDESTRÖM'S DESCRIPTION
OF NEW SWEDEN.

A brief account and description of New Sweden's location and the reasons for its founding, accompanied by a map with scales in degrees in miles, each degree covering 15 miles.

Cape Hinlopen lies at 36 degrees and 30 minutes latitude. The bay between Cape Hinlopen and Cape May is roughly five miles across. To the southwest of Cape May, there are three sandbanks in a row, not deep under the water, making navigation between them unsafe. The safest route is to pass between them and Cape May.

⁶ Known to the Swedes as Fort Trefaldighet.

This is followed by detailed directions for navigating Delaware Bay.

...until one comes to a place called Narateromp,⁷ which lies to port. Continuing northwards past Beaver Island to starboard and sailing east northeast for a quarter of a mile we reach Fort Nassau. It is then 2 and a half miles from Fort Nassau to Fogelsand, a wide sandbank lying north of [Summer?].

After a number of sailing directions, Sandkikan (modern-day Trenton, New Jersey) is the furthest upstream location mentioned.

At Oytseasing⁸ and as far as a place named Asamohacking,⁹ there is a kind of black soil mixed with clay, baked in the sun. The Swedes have had a fort (Elfsborg) on the bank between Oytseasing and Asamohacking, but after a time of abandonment, it fell into ruin and was furthermore entirely burned to its foundation and destroyed by the Lenape.

From Obisquahosit¹⁰ to Narraticons there grows an abundance of calmus¹¹. From Oytseasing as far as Kagkikanizackiens creek, there is black soil mixed with sand. This is a fertile area and suitable for plantations, where all kinds of crops could grow abundantly, especially tobacco. In the area between Memirako and Mantua creek, there grows an abundance of walnut, chestnut, persimmon, wheat, cumin, cypress and mulberries, as well as many other trees that cannot be identified and are not found in any other places along the river.

All along the river's edge from Caman¹² to Tetamekonchz Creek¹³ and in most parts in between, are channels cutting into the land, and within the woods grow large amounts of white, purple, blue and red grapes. From Kagkikanizackiens to Memiraco, along the east bank of the river there are reefs and shallows so that it is no deeper than 16 feet in some places. Arwames¹⁴ where the Dutch had a fort¹⁵ has been burned down by our Lenape. This would be a good site to build a town. Persimmon grows here, and sweet-smelling sassafras trees. At

⁷ Raccoon Creek, New Jersey

⁸ Near Fort Elfsborg

⁹ Salem Creek, New Jersey

¹⁰ Penn's Neck, New Jersey

¹¹ *Acorus calamus* (also called sweet flag), a wetland plant often used in traditional medicine over centuries to treat digestive disorders.

¹² Possibly Camden, New Jersey

¹³ Big Timber Creek, New Jersey

¹⁴ Little Timber Creek, New Jersey

¹⁵ Nassau

Arvames, the river begins to regain a good depth and along the bank it is inconvenient for troops to come ashore.

At Sinsessing, trees grow which smell like raw fish, the wood of which does not burn properly. Between here and Aquikonasra,¹⁶ the land is high and not very suitable for cultivation. From Tekoke to Qvinkorenning, the land is flat and good, but the coast there is shallow. At Sinsessing, the Lenape often catch plenty of sturgeon, turtles and other fish. At Poenpishing there are maple, beech and alders growing. Near Rancocas creek there are wild hops growing and around Ashiung, hemp.

This river is populated by various native peoples, each having their own particular territory and each overseen by a leader or sachem. These places are called Poastquessing, Pemieckpacka, Veqviqucske, Vicka Konick, Passayunk and Nittabakonk. The resident sachems are Ahopameck and his brother Quirocus, Peminacka, Speckveymotto, Juneker, Mattaviracka, Schalihi, Vinangene, and Naaman.

At Mordare creek, there is black clay which, when dried and prepared, could be used to make ink and is as good as charcoal in that respect. Between Mordare and Waryn creeks mulberries, cypress and fruit trees, two or three armfuls thick, grow plentifully. The shore there is lined by meadows. From Neeyeck to Poastquessing creek, the land is not settled by either natives or Christians, though it appears fertile, and there are no obstacles along the river's edge to hinder access to land. At Waryn creek, there is blue clay which, when properly tempered and used, would serve well as a dye.

From Qvincorening to Rancoques, the land is somewhat hilly and inconvenient with barriers for approaching the shore, yet Rancoques is a remarkable creek, navigable by large vessels, the only shame being that there is a shoal right in the middle to the south. At Spinneludden sea creatures are driven up onto the shore which cannot return to the sea by themselves. When they are well-cooked and prepared, they taste as good as lobster. There is blue clay here as well.

From Rancoques creek to Wirantapecka, there is good land covered in spruce, not suitable for maize but good for tobacco and other crops. The shore is rocky and inconvenient for landing. All along the shore as far as Bombay hook, large oysters can be found along the shoreline on both sides of the bay. Walnuts, chestnuts, cypress, and Persimmon

¹⁶ Petty Island, between Philadelphia and New Jersey.

trees grow here. From Wirantapecka to Tacony, the land is high yet well-drained and fertile, and the river is shallow. The shore is rocky with many lupine bushes growing there, suggesting fertile soil.

From Tacony up along the eastern side of the river, the land is pleasant and suitable for maize cultivation, which the native people have been planting there for many years. The land is hard to reach except by canoe. Only a few live on the eastern side, inhabited by the Mantuser, a people who claim a just title of possession to the river, though now much reduced by war. The land here is very rich in beaver, otter, raccoons, mink, wild cats, moose, bears, wolves, deer and lions¹⁷, along with all manner of other wild animals.

At Tyhlara, there is an abundance of all types of fish: sturgeon, pike, perch, as well as turtles. Both the land and the sea turtle, when well prepared, is as good meat as you could find. There is also a large number of swans, geese, gulls, doves, and other wild birds in this river.

From Sipaissing to Neeyeck Creek, there is good land although it doesn't stretch as far inland, instead curving around the creeks, with beautiful pastures to be found. Farther up, it is convenient for settlement and, in some areas, suitable for building mills. In Hwijter's creek, or Svapeiksisko, there is fine white clay which could be of use when dried and tempered. At Rothebohans' island, red clay can be found.

At Hviskakimensi Creek, or Sippus, there is red clay that, when prepared properly, could serve as a substitute for cinnabar. At Skildhpädde¹⁸ Falls, there are many turtles whose shells can serve many uses. Along this side from Wyndrufwa¹⁹ Point near Nittabakonk, white, brown, blue and red grapes grow abundantly. At Timman's shore, there is yellow clay which, when dried, is like ochre, though here it is used only for dying hides with. In this area walnuts and chestnuts grow, along with sassafras trees. The creek can be navigated by canoe at high water up to Kingsessing.

The best pines grow at Manajonck; linden trees grow there too. From Lyland to Menaharon and surrounding is low-lying land with fertile maize fields and has been cultivated for a long time about a mile inland

¹⁷ Likely a reference to pumas or cougars.

¹⁸ Turtle Falls.

¹⁹ Grape Point.

from the river. Further inland can be found more land suitable for maize and would be suitable for Christians.

The northern side of Aquikonasra cannot be traversed with a canoe at low water. At the falls Asinpink creek, the water is two fathoms deep, and there are three navigable creeks along this stretch: Poatqvessing, Pemickpacka, and Mencysashi Creek, where mills could be built. Poatqvessing Creek, in particular, has by nature been blessed by all the amenities one could want. It has high land on both sides, and the falls could be fitted with a pulley for raising goods and people. Pemickpacka is not as convenient due to dryness in the summer, but the land here is good.

Mencieck is a large creek, though not as amenable as Poatqvessing. On the southern side of the river near Mechechason, there are rocky hills where ore could be mined. At the plantation there grows a plant called callibas, which is very nice when the seeds are removed. To the south of Tinne Konck island is a small lake, always full of birds. In Wirantapecka creek to the south of the river, there is a warm, sheltered area that never freezes, where swans gather. Kikimen's creek can be navigated by a boat at high tide. At Mirekat creek, hops grow, and there are plums, mulberries and chestnut trees nearby.

At Vickacks Sippus or Budan creek, persimmon and grapes grow, along with thickets of spruce. At Sipassing, the land could support a hundred families. Near and around Menahickan grow white, black, blue, and red berries. In the winter season, at Sankikan, berries grow that remain on the branch all through winter. Around Aluming falls grow walnuts, chestnuts, persimmon, mulberries, plums and krikon, as well as grapevines, hemp and wild hops.

At Asinpink Falls, the Lenape catch a type of fish they call *kwalt*, which they sell to the Christians. It is a long and thick fish with black stripes running lengthwise. There are also many kinds of venomous snakes, the age of which can be reckoned by counting the rings on their tails. One found near May's Plantation was said to be around 14 years old by the Dutch. When these snakes become angry, they rattle and the sound can be heard from far away. At that moment, it is not safe to approach them.

This new map with rivers and land surveyed, as well as the ruins of Fort Christina and new fortifications, made in the years 1654-1655 by Peter Lindeström, engineer of fortifications.

Vol. 196, ff.14r-
22r, 1654.
Swedish.

3. Copy of the above.

Vol. 196, f.25r, 18
May 1693.
Swedish.

4. PETITION FROM PETER LINDESTRÖM'S WIDOW,
MARGARETHA ROOS

A widow named Margaretha Roos, who in her first marriage was wed to the Secretary Samuel Kämpensköld, and in her second marriage to the engineer Per Lindeström, delivered to His Royal Highness a book with drawings and descriptions of New Sweden in the West Indies, where the aforementioned Lindeström had served as engineer. This book, which he compiled in his final years and during his illness, was dedicated to His Royal Highness and contains many beautiful and curious items, as is well known to His Excellency the Councillor and Governor Count Gyldenstolpe. Along with this, she humbly petitions:

For assistance with a decent burial for her late husband, as she suffers great poverty, engineer Lindeström having been bedridden and sick for many years and having spent his meager fortune on treatments, so his widow finds herself in considerable debt and destitution.

She requests to be granted three homesteads, as she is now approaching sixty years of age, which her husband had once held during his lifetime, namely: Norra Hult in the parish of Millesviks and Norra Grimbråten in the parish of Ölserud. Neither of these are believed to have been reassigned since Lindeström's death, as the Crown's bailiff has declared that the rents should be delivered to him.

Vol. 196, f.26r-
26v, 18 May 1693.
Swedish.

5. PETITION FROM PETER LINDESTRÖM'S WIDOW,
MARGARETHA ROOS

Royal and Most Gracious Highness,

At the feet of Your Royal Highness, I, a poor old widow, in the deepest humility, present my late husband Peter Lindeström's work, a geography and description of New Sweden in America, where he served as an engineer for the Swedish Crown. This work, which he did not complete before his death on the 22nd of December, had occupied him during his advanced age and the last eight years of severe illness, bedridden as he was and in great suffering. Even then, he did not neglect his efforts on this work, despite the lack of light and peace, and his scant means did not allow him to bring it to completion during his lifetime. In humblest devotion, I now present this work to Your Royal Highness, as was his wish, though he was called away before he could personally dedicate it to Your Royal Highness. His wish was that it should not be abandoned and so I present this book to Your Royal Highness, humbly requesting that you graciously accept it and, in your mercy, grant some relief to me, your poor old servant, until my death.

This is followed by an archival note concerning the removal of the accompanying map from the collection.

Vol. 196, ff.27r-
27v, 18 May 1693.
Swedish.

6. PETITION FROM PETER LINDESTRÖM'S WIDOW,
MARGARETHA ROOS

Your Royal Majesty, I humbly and sorrowfully bring to Your attention that my husband, the land surveyor and engineer in New Sweden, Peter Lindström, has now passed away. For twelve long years, he suffered from an enduring illness, bedridden continuously, yet he remained diligent in his work almost until the end. He spent all his modest means on physicians and medicines, leaving nothing with which I can provide for his burial.

I therefore humbly implore Your Royal Majesty to extend gracious aid, considering his miserable state during his lifetime and his service to the Crown. With the greatest diligence before his death, he left behind a geography of New Sweden in America, which, following his final wishes, I present herewith to Your Royal Majesty.

I beg Your Majesty to grant some small burial assistance and also to show merciful consideration to the two estates in Värmland: Norra Grimbråten in the parish of Ölserud and Norra Hult in the parish of Millesviks. If it pleases Your Royal Majesty to mercifully grant these estates to me for my lifetime, as I am a sickly, impoverished widow over sixty years of age whose remaining days cannot be many.

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| <p>Vol. 196, ff.31r-45r, May 1648.
Dutch.</p> | <p>7.</p> | <p>HENRIK HUYGEN'S DEBT BOOK</p> <p>Many pages damaged.</p> |
| <p>Vol. 196, f.109r-141r, 1642-1646.
German.</p> | <p>8.</p> | <p>ACCOUNT BOOK FROM FORT CHRISTINA</p> <p>Many pages damaged.</p> |
| <p>Vol. 196, f.144r-225v, 1639.
Dutch.</p> | <p>9.</p> | <p>LIST OF DEBTORS</p> <p>Many pages damaged.</p> |
| <p>Vol. 196, ff.226r-226v. 1641.
German.</p> | <p>10.</p> | <p>LIST OF PEOPLE WHO SAILED ON THE CHARITAS TO NEW SWEDEN IN 1641</p> <p>See Johnson, <i>Swedish settlements</i> vol.1 p.151.</p> |
| <p>Vol. 196, ff.229r-230r. 1641.
German.</p> | <p>11.</p> | <p>Partly a copy of the preceding, damaged text.</p> |
| <p>Vol. 196, ff.231r-240v. 1644.
German.</p> | <p>12-15</p> | <p>LISTS OF THE INHABITANTS OF NEW SWEDEN IN 1644, 1648 and 1649.</p> <p>See Johnson, <i>Swedish settlements</i> vol.2 p.700.</p> |
| <p>Vol. 196, f.242r. 1655. Swedish.</p> | <p>16.</p> | <p>LIST OF THOSE TO RECEIVE MONEY BY ORDER OF GOVERNOR JOHAN RISINGH</p> |

	Riksdalers
Lieutenant Sven Höök	16
Engineer Peter Lindström	12
Ensign Peter Wendel	12
Pastor Mattias Nertunius	10
Peter Hiortt	6
Clerk of stores Peter Mörtt	8
Armorer Anders Kiämpe	6
Corporal Anders Olofson	5
Drummer Sven Anderson	6
Björn Oloffson	5
Soldier Lars Esbjörnson	4
Mårten Crum	4
Hans Prijs	4
Lars Jonson	4
Carl Julius	8
Soldier Anders Kiäpme	4
Håkan Åkerman	4
Hans Ekor	4
Påwel Kvist	4
Erich Bengtson	4

Vol. 196, f. 243r.
1648. German.

17. PASSENGERS WHO RETURNED ON THE SWAN

The following individuals arrived from New Sweden on the ship,
The Swan, and claim the following sums from the Company:

	Florins
Johannes Campanius, preacher	775:15.6
Måns Nielsen Klingh, lieutenant	2599:12
Knut Lilliehöök, junker	296:19
Friederich Hans Koch, barber	225
Hans Rossbrack, blacksmith	1311:13
Additional (for blacksmith tools)	24
Erich Andersson, trumpeter	216:14
Deduction for a soldier's pay	49:12
Måns Nilsson, soldier	20:10
Erich [Åkesson?], deceased soldier	263:3
Johan Andersson, soldier	145:5
Anders [Larsson?], cattle keeper	368
Total	6296:3.6

Vol. 196, f.244r.
1646. Swedish.

18. PETITION FROM MICHEL JOHANSON

Most Mighty and Gracious Majesty,

I, a poor elderly man and servant of the Crown, am compelled to submit this humble supplication to recount how I, at one time, served under the Royal Admiralty and in the Crown's service in the Baltic Sea as well as Virginia, having been employed as a scribe. This was until I, during the recent Danish battles in the year 1645, was injured, rendering me unfit for further service at sea, as evidenced by the attached copy of the Royal Admiralty's pass. Since my return home, I have only received the sum of 14 dalers and 25½ öre in wages for the years 1643, 1644, and 1645, as the Royal Admiralty's records will confirm. Despite making humble petitions for the payment of my remaining wages, no claim has been honored to this day.

Now, in my poverty and misery, I am entirely destitute and in great need. Therefore, I most humbly beseech, in the weakness of my old age, that Your Majesty might graciously consider my modest and faithful service, and the penury of my old age, during which I have persisted despite frailty, and now bestow upon me Your most gracious favour, making sufficient provision to sustain myself and my poor household in my old age.

Your most humble and devoted servant,

Michels Johanson, formerly secretary aboard the ship Kalmar Nyckel.

Vol. 196, f.245r. 2
September 1646.
Swedish.

19. RESPONSE FROM THE COUNCIL OF STATE (RIKSRÅD)
AND ADMIRALTY TO MICHEL JOHANSON

We, the undersigned, Councillors of the Realm and Admirals of the Kingdom of Sweden, hereby make it known that, as the bearer, Michel Johanson, has for some years served as a secretary aboard ships under Her Majesty the Queen of Sweden and the Admiralty of the Realm and has during that time undertaken voyages to Virginia, and now desires to seek his fortune in other endeavours, we, upon his humble request, released him from Admiralty service a couple of years ago.

We therefore request, on behalf of Her Majesty the Queen and the Royal Admiralty, that all those with whom he may come into contact allow him free and unhindered passage to whatever place he intends to travel. This is hereby attested with our signatures and the seal of the Royal Admiralty.

Dated in Stockholm, September 2, 1646 on behalf of the Royal Admiralty, Tyress Ammundsson.

Vol. 196, f.246r.
1650s-1660s.
Swedish.

20. PETITION FROM MICHEL JOHANSON

Most Mighty and Gracious Majesty,

With this new most humble petition, I am compelled to respectfully bring to Your Majesty's attention that I have served under His Royal Majesty and the Admiralty of the Realm as a scribe aboard a ship and, during that time, was employed on voyages to Virginia and the West Indies, as evidenced by the enclosed pass issued by the Royal Admiralty and dated 2 September 1646.

This was graciously granted to me, yet during these voyages, I endured much hardship, particularly on 7 August 1645 during the Danish war when the Kalmar Nyckel was attacked by a Danish ship named St.Peer between Malmö and Copenhagen. Of the crew of the Kalmar Nyckel, only twelve men, including officers and enlisted men, survived. I, a poor man, was wounded and must now live in distress and great poverty with a crippled body, over which I pray God may show mercy.

Despite this, I have humbly petitioned regarding my remaining wages. For the year ending 2 November, when I arrived in Stockholm, I received only 14 dalers and 25½ öre in silver, as evidenced by the note from the regimental clerk, the late Daniel Mårthensson. This sum was delivered to me from the Admiralty's treasury, yet nothing further has been paid, as the Royal Admiralty's books clearly show what I received during these years.

However, after leaving the Admiralty's service, I entered the service of the late master of the mint Daniel Kock and worked in the western ironworks district, where I remained for 16 years, as my documents attest. Consequently, my claim has been hindered, while my fellow shipmates have received their remaining dues. I

have made several humble appeals to the Royal Admiralty, but to this day, I have been unable to obtain the smallest amount.

Therefore, I now throw myself upon Your Royal Majesty's most gracious mercy, which regards the plight of all those in hardship, among whom I count myself, as one who has served the Crown and is now left disabled. I humbly beg that I may receive what I am owed to sustain myself and my poor household in my great poverty and infirmity.

An archival note is appended to the date 1646 noting that 1662 is the earliest year this could have been written. The text also refers to the "late" master of the mint Daniel Kock who died in 1650.

Vol. 196, f.247r. 2
September 1646.
Swedish.

21. RESPONSE FROM THE COUNCIL OF STATE (RIKSRÅD)
AND ADMIRALTY TO MICHELS JOHANSON

Copy of 20. above.

Vol. 196, f.248r.
12 August 1645.
Swedish.

22. PETITION FROM FORMER CREW OF THE *KALMAR*
NYCKEL

Most noble and gracious Queen, may it please Her Royal Highness to know of our humble and loyal service and obedience, always ready to serve. We, poor sailors appealing in all humility to Your Majesty on 12 August 1645, submitted a rightful claim regarding the West India voyage to the Admiralty. However, regarding said rightful claim—though we have endured great hardship and distress, petitioning persistently for two years with the utmost diligence and effort, we have been unable to obtain full satisfaction.

The money, which we rightfully deserve for our efforts and sacrifices, has been withheld despite the fact that we, during the journey and earlier in the Jutland expeditions, endured significant hardship and distress. We now find ourselves in such a dire situation that we have no other recourse but to rely on begging. Therefore, in all humility, and with God's blessing, we turn to Her Royal Majesty, beseeching, for the sake of Christ and justice, that our great need, suffering, and distress may be graciously considered.

Vol. 196, f.249r.
12 August 1645.
Swedish.

23. RESPONSE FROM QUEEN CHRISTINA TO A PETITION
FROM THE SAILORS OF VARIOUS EXPEDITIONS TO NEW
SWEDEN

In the years 1642 and 1643, it was approved and resolved by our then-regents and government that the warships *Svanen* and *Fama* (in the first expedition) and *Kalmar Nyckel* and *Gripen* (in the second expedition) would sail to New Sweden in the West Indies and be outfitted and provided for at the Crown's expense. Now, however, the sailors who were employed on said expeditions daily come before us and complain, alleging that much is still owed to them for their service. They most humbly request to be compensated for what is due to them.

Our gracious will and command are thus that you take steps to ensure that these sailors are satisfied with payment from the Admiralty's funds and that the South Company is freed from all costs related to the outfitting of the mentioned ships for their two previous expeditions.

From Stockholm, 12 August 1645, Christina.

Vol. 196, f.250r. 1
April 1648.
Swedish.

24. PERMISSION FROM JOHAN PRINTZ FOR AN ELDERLY
SETTLER TO RETURN BACK TO SWEDEN

To Her Majesty the Queen, Most Gracious Sovereign, from Your Humble Servant and Appointed Governor of New Sweden,

I, Johan Printz wish to make known that the bearer of this pass, Christoffer [Rätten?], has lived and worked here in New Sweden as a free man for seven years. However, as he has lost his wife here, and most of his children have departed him through marriage and other circumstances, and being an elderly man, he is no longer able to cultivate the land here by himself. Therefore, he has requested to return home to Sweden, which, in consideration of the long time he has lived here, as well as his advanced age and personal losses, cannot be denied him. He has accordingly been provided with a passport and discharge, enabling his return along with his fourteen-year-old son.

To all whom it may concern, and to each and every one in particular, my request is that they honor this my passport, grant him goodwill, and offer him all due assistance. This is only fitting given his years of service and in anticipation of similar treatment for myself in like or other circumstances. For confirmation, I have signed this document and affixed my seal.

Johan Printz, New Gothenburg, 1 April 1648.

Vol. 196, f.251r.
1652 Swedish.

25. PETITION FROM HANS HANSSON, HANS PERSSON,
DANIEL LARSSON, FORMER CREW OF THE *KATTAN*

Petition (badly damaged, text missing from right-hand side) written in 1652 by several individuals requesting aid. They describe the hardship they are experiencing after their ship, the *Katten*, sank near Puerto Rico. Afterward, they sought refuge on that island, where they were plundered and taken captive. The petitioners mention their dire financial situation and request that they be granted money to help them survive through difficult times.

Vol. 196, f.252r.
18 August 1652.
Dutch.

26. PASS GIVEN BY GOVERNOR PRINTZ AT NEW
GOTHENBORG TO LAURENS CORNELIUS ANDRIESEN

From the Governor of New Sweden, Johan Printz, addressed to the Queen of Sweden. Notes that Laurens Andries Cuijper, who had served in New Sweden for about eleven and a half years, has requested permission to return to Sweden, and this request was granted. The letter instructs that the aforementioned be allowed to pass freely through all territories under Swedish control, with all due respect and consideration for his needs during the journey. The letter requests that all military and other officials respect the permission granted to Cuijper and ensure that he is treated with the utmost regard and provided assistance as needed for his voyage.

27. OATH OF ALLEGIANCE FOR THE POPULATION OF NEW
SWEDEN, 1654

Vol. 196, f.253r. 9
June 1654.
Swedish.

The text begins with an affirmation by the signatories swearing allegiance to the Swedish monarchy. They pledge to be loyal and obedient to the crown and to serve the land and its rulers as dictated by the royal will. The document states that they will govern the land in accordance with the laws and ordinances of Sweden. They are committed to upholding the law, ensuring order, and preventing rebellion or disorder within the land. It is emphasised that the signatories will follow both divine law (in terms of the Christian faith) and secular law (the laws of the Swedish kingdom). This includes adhering to the commands of the monarchy, military obligations, and other state regulations. Duty to protect and support the land, people, and government, ensuring the welfare of both individuals and the state. They mention that they will act in the best interest of the country, protecting it from external and internal threats. There is a passage indicating that no trade or commercial activity should take place without the royal permission, and that all actions must be in line with the royal authority. This includes restrictions on dealings that could go against royal orders or cause harm to the state. The document concludes with a formal declaration that the signatories are bound by these commitments

Vol. 196, f.256r.
c.1654-55.
Swedish.

28. PETITION FROM CHRISTOPHER R[?]LL TO THE QUEEN

I humbly acknowledge and inform Your Majesty that I had the honour of being sent to New Sweden, where I took possession of a plot of land for settlement, with the intention of securing my livelihood. However, since God has called my wife and children away, I am no longer able to manage the business and expenses of this venture, which I had hoped to support through my work. Thus, in my poverty, I am left without the means to cover the costs and expenses incurred. Therefore, I humbly and respectfully request that Your Majesty might, in Your great mercy, consider my great hardship and grant me a favourable response, possibly as recompense for the considerable expenses, labour, and travel I have endured.

29. PETITION FROM GÖRAN HENDRICKSSON TO THE QUEEN

Vol. 196, f.257r.
c.1654-55.
Swedish.

Most gracious Majesty,

In all humility, I bring before Your Royal Majesty that I have, for many years, served the Crown as a charcoal burner, as my documents and proofs will show. I have worked as both a charcoal burner and a tar burner for the Crown, and now that I have learned of Your Majesty's most gracious desire to send people to New Sweden, I have prepared myself to join those being sent.

However, as I reflect upon this, I find myself without sufficient means to support myself and my poor small children. I have appealed to the honourable Commandant and presented my case to him, but I now humbly petition Your Royal Majesty. I ask, in Your Majesty's great mercy and grace, that You might grant me a small allowance for myself and my children, or else graciously provide for us in some way. Without such assistance, I fear that hunger and poverty will force me to remain behind and forego this proposed journey.

Should God help us to reach New Sweden, I will, with my hands, work diligently at producing charcoal and tar, ensuring that I am no burden either to the authorities or to anyone else. I humbly hope for Your Majesty's most gracious assistance and remain,

Your Majesty's most humble and faithful subject,

Jöran Hendrichsson

Vol. 196, f.258r. 1
December 1655.
Swedish.

30. TESTIMONIAL AND PASS FOR PETER LINDESTRÖM,
ENGINEER, ISSUED BY GOVERNOR JOHAN RISINGH

Johan Risingh, Director of New Sweden, issues a testimonial for Peter Lindeström, an engineer serving the Swedish Crown and the South Company. Lindeström is returning to Sweden after unexpected enemy attacks on the colony. Risingh commends Lindeström's faithful service and diligent execution of his duties, requesting that higher authorities reward and promote him for his contributions. Document written aboard the ship Björnen in the canal.

- Vol. 196, f.262r.
10 July 1644.
Dutch.
31. RECEIPT OF CONSIGNMENT OF GOODS ON THE SHIP
FAMA FROM JOHAN PRINTZ.
- Vol. 196, ff.263r-
271v. 1641.
Dutch.
32. DEBT LEDGER
- Vol. 196, ff.276r-
287r. January
1658. Swedish.
33. JOHAN RISINGH'S DESCRIPTION OF NEW SWEDEN
- Divided into five parts with subdivisions:
- I. A brief account of the land.
 - II. Our rights and claims to it against others.
 - III. How colonies may be established there, as well as how trade and commerce upon it could be properly directed so that the land could be settled and yield good benefits for both the Crown and its inhabitants.
 - IV. What kinds of resources and income could be obtained from it.
 - V. Consideration of the damage and wrongs committed by the Dutch against the Swedes in their incursions.
- I. A Description of New Sweden
- New Sweden is located in the northern part of America, between 38- and 40-degrees latitude north, along the same parallel as Flanders in Europe and Lisbon in Portugal, and at 316 degrees longitude. It stretches from the mouth of the river for 30 Swedish miles upstream to its source. The tide ebbs and flows every six hours so high that vessels can sail upon it. The coastline from the river's mouth at Cape May and Cape Henlopen is long and reaches up to the trees, being about a mile wide in some parts. The Indigenous people call it Poutaxat, the English Delaware, and the Dutch the South River of New Netherland, though it is also known as Sweden's River.

This is a most beautiful land, with a healthy climate, especially on the western side, and fertile soil that can yield all the grains and fruits that grow in these parts of Europe. The land is richly endowed with a variety of beautiful trees, such as walnut, oak (which is highly suitable for construction), mulberries, chestnut, apples, plums, and persimmon. Without doubt, many other valuable plants could be successfully grown there, such as wine grapes and the best varieties of apples. The eastern shore, however, is sandy and marshy, unhealthy, and less fruitful, though some fertile and promising areas can still be found. The soil there can yield crops when properly cultivated. It is likely that resources such as gold or silver could be discovered further inland and upriver.

The region is also richly endowed with various kinds of fish. Large salmon can be found at the river's mouth, and lamprey, bass, herring, and others migrate there with the tide. The bays are abundant with crabs and oysters, while cod and mackerel are plentiful on the offshore banks. This land and its river are excellently situated for trade and commerce, both with Natives and Christians. Being centrally located on the coasts of America, it is well-placed to receive ships traveling both north and south. In short, this is a pleasant, healthy, and well-situated land, as good as any in Europe. A more detailed description can confirm this thoroughly.

II. The Swedes' rights to this land are thus confirmed.

1. It can be demonstrated by good reason and documents that our Swedes, with lawful right, were the first to take possession of this land after the Dutch had practically abandoned it. Namely, based on a letter from the Dutch East India Company dated 1 October 1630, which should be available in the records of the American Company, from which those men first received the area in 1636. It is well established that our Swedish colony was first established and built at Fort Christina.

2. Furthermore, the Swedes acquired this land lawfully from its rightful owners, purchasing it piece by piece. This land was then subsequently taken into possession. The purchase deeds from the transactions with the Indians and the physical acknowledgment of occupation serve as proof.

3. It is also widely reported that King Charles I of England relinquished all claims to this land to the Swedes during the reign of King Gustavus Adolphus, when Count Johan Oxenstierna served as ambassador to England in 1630.

4. According to all customary laws among nations, the Swedes hold the strongest claims to this land, based on the four recognized legal grounds for land acquisition: (1) *occupatio* (occupation), (2) *donatio* (donation), (3) *emptio a justo possessore* (purchase from the rightful owner), and (4) *investitura et incorporatio* (investiture and incorporation). Discovery alone cannot establish a solid right to the claimed New Sweden. This is demonstrated by the example of the Spaniards, who discovered and charted the entire coasts of the Americas from Florida to the Davis Strait. However, despite their claims, the Spaniards do not possess all the lands between the Davis Strait and Florida to this day. Just as the Spaniards cannot assert full rights based solely on their initial discovery, so too cannot the English or Dutch, who later charted and claimed these lands, but without the supporting titles to establish true ownership.

The act of discovery or mapping, even if the land is unoccupied, does not confer full rights unless one incorporates, settles, and governs the land, maintaining it without being forcibly expelled. If the territory is abandoned, another may easily take possession, which undermines the original claim. The Dutch have no better or more legitimate title to New Netherland than can be proven through their actions. Their claim rests only on having established themselves and their colonies along the North River (Hudson River), where no one previously held possession. Although the English argue that they claimed the North River through Captain Hudson's exploration under an English commission during the reign of James of England, Hudson did not settle or occupy the land. Instead, he merely named the bay after himself. Before Hudson, Sebastian Cabot, a Venetian, had also charted parts of the Americas from the 67th to the 30th degrees of latitude, further complicating the competing claims of the English and Dutch, who dispute under whose commission Hudson conducted his voyage.

Donatio is a title the English place great emphasis on. They argue that King Henry granted all of North America to be settled and possessed, and that James granted Lord George Calvert, Lord

Baltimore of Ireland, the region called Maryland for settlement and occupation. Likewise, regions to the north, including New England, which encompasses New Sweden, were granted. These claims were protested by our representatives in New Sweden in 1654. It was demonstrated that such letters of donation or grants from King James, as the English claim, hold the same weight as the gift King Ferdinand of Castile made to grant all of the West Indies under the Prime Meridian westward, or as the Portuguese king's grants of coasts in Africa and Asia and all of the East Indies. Just as these extravagant grants held no value when the donor lacked rightful ownership unless the territories were acquired through rightful means, so too were James's grants empty of value.

Thus, the English, like the French and Dutch, could not validate their claims solely through royal gifts or papal grants. Countries have established such claims through occupying lands in Africa and the West and East Indies, but they must take possession, settle, and justify their claims through lawful governance. The English claims under Lord Baltimore are likewise invalid as they never took true possession or established governance over New Sweden. By contrast, the Swedish claims stand on firmer ground, having been legitimately acquired, taken into possession, and governed under rightful agreements with indigenous owners and formal acts of settlement.

The third rightful title is *possessio tenarum* and *justus possessor*.

Now we Swedes have divided and purchased the land, from the headland or the river's mouth all the way to the river's source, and have lawfully settled it. Neither the English nor the Dutch, in all their conflicts, have ever owned or possessed this land. We Swedes have lawfully invested in and inhabited it, so no one can rightfully dispute this against us without resorting to violence.

The Dutch, under the West India Company, have had colonies here along the river, but they were not firmly established. One was at [Horn?kylen] near the bay's entrance, where the Indians destroyed it and later sold the land to us. Another colony they had was farther up the river at Tinecum, consisting of only a few families, which later moved farther down and called it Fort Nassau. Subsequently, they moved even farther down and built a fortified redoubt there, on land that was rightfully ours, purchased and clearly marked as ours by a pole. Despite this, they

removed the pole and unlawfully and unjustly forced their way in, disregarding all protests made by our officials against such actions. Their redoubt, which they named Fort Casimir, was abandoned to us Swedes with the arrival of the ship Örn in 1654. All Dutch colonists living there submitted to the Swedish Crown and swore their allegiance.

Those in Amsterdam who had been commissioned by the East India Company to occupy this river—namely, Albert Burgh and, in his absence, Joannes de Laet and Samuel Blommaert—have ceded it to the Swedes, as Mr. Minuit's documents will show. Therefore, the Dutch had no legitimate claims to this entire river or any part of it after we took possession and documents—including written agreements with the Indians and witness testimonies—will demonstrate our rightful claim to this river and land.

Regarding the discovery of this land, those who claim it have no legitimacy. The Spanish were the first discoverers, and after them, the English, who assert that they discovered the 'North River' by means of Captain Hudson, acting under King James's commission, where New Amsterdam now stands. The Dutch counterclaim that they purchased all of Hudson's rights and charter and that they settled there near Hudson's Bay in 1610. The English Governor in Virginia protested this, noting that the Dutch were under English authority and allegiance. Later, however, the Dutch received reinforcements from Holland, established themselves there under a new governor, and fortified their position. Nevertheless, they had no claims in New Sweden, even to what they call the 'South River'. Thus, the Dutch cannot, with any legitimacy, demonstrate their right to this river or its surrounding lands under the titles of possession, but only through violence and repeated incursions.

III. How colonies may be established there

1. At home, significant capital in gold should be collected from the entire realm and the provinces, including contributions from wealthy nobles and cities. To reclaim the land from desolation, settle it, cultivate it and plant it, substantial capital is required. This is also necessary for fortifying the area against enemies.
2. To manage this capital, certain committees should be established to manage these funds. These committees would oversee

expenditure and revenue, issue orders for shipping and trade, and ensure that both the trade and the capital increase rather than diminish. One chamber could be located in Stockholm, another in Wismar and a third in Gothenburg, or wherever fitting out ships can be done most efficiently. Factors such as the good pricing of provisions and freight goods, the availability of seamen, and the quick loading and unloading of ships must be considered, so that each ship can make two to three voyages per year. Company houses should be set up in these locations, where the returns brought back by the ships would immediately be stored. The ships would then be resupplied with new cargo, crew, and equipment, and sent off again.

3. Once a year, these committees should send representatives to Gothenburg to present their accounts. Together, they would conclude on the direction and oversight of the entire operation.
4. The directors should be chosen by the primary participants, namely those who contributed at least a twentieth share of the capital. Directors should rotate every three years. These should be competent men experienced in trade, honest and upright, who will not interfere with the company for personal gain or use it to enrich themselves improperly.
5. All committees should operate justly, without regard for persons, whether of higher or lower status. Profits should be distributed proportionally, so that each participant, whether they have contributed the least or the most, receives their fair share. Furthermore, since the company is endowed and authorized with such privileges by the highest authority, neither nobility, magistrates, nor other officials should infringe upon the company's privileges or statutes, nor cause harm to its profits or capital without incurring penalties.

The Company's Direction Could Be Best Organized as Follows:

1. A capable governor should be appointed, skilled in matters of governance and war, as well as trade and agriculture. This individual must be prudent, diligent in all matters, good and honest, and above all, God-fearing. Those selected for advisory and other service roles should possess the same virtues. The necessary number of such individuals should be appointed as the work requires. Their instructions and statutes should be

devised by the governor in consultation with the council and approved collectively by the directors at home.

2. A swift course of trade should be established and maintained between home and abroad, ensuring goods are not left sitting idle, resulting in loss of time and profit. This is crucial, as it is the very soul of the entire operation.
3. Efforts should be made to secure a base or warehouse on one of the Caribbean islands. All goods traded or produced in New Sweden could be transported there with short voyages and stored. These would include tobacco, sugar, and other items, which could then be sent home in ships. Ships arriving there could unload their cargo and immediately return home, while other ships from Sweden could arrive and carry on the same process. With this system, voyages could be doubled or even tripled annually, significantly increasing profits and reducing costs. Furthermore, the crew would be less likely to fall ill or die during these trips. Reliable factors and merchants should be placed in the towns, working in agreement with the English or French, to ensure the ships are well-provisioned and that New Sweden gradually becomes self-sufficient.
4. Good order in matters of religion and worship should be upheld. Similarly, attention must be given to the maintenance of the poor and the employment and sustenance of all inhabitants.
5. The council's governance should adhere to sound policies, while law and justice should be administered through lawful trials and procedures.
6. The region's defences should include fortifications, soldiers, ships, boat crews, and farmers, along with adequate ammunition and other necessary provisions.
7. The land should be cultivated and settled to ensure sustainable prosperity. This includes agricultural activities, plantations, the establishment of cities, churches, and villages, the promotion of crafts, trade, and shipbuilding, and the management of all goods entering and leaving the region. This includes timber production, sawmills, ship construction, fishing, freight, hunting of game and birds, and the extraction of any metals that may be discovered.

IV. What kinds of resources and income could be obtained from the colony.

The following benefits could be derived from New Sweden: agriculture, livestock farming, hunting, forestry and gardens, mining, craftsmanship, and shipping. Through these activities, this fertile and well-situated land could be developed into a flourishing province of the Crown. Cities, villages, counties, and manors could be established, providing revenue to the Crown and employment to thousands who currently live in poverty. Trade and shipping would increase, and the population would gain expertise in navigation and other trades, reducing idleness and disorder.

1. Agriculture or farming could bring great benefits due to the soil's abundant fertility, suitable for all kinds of crops found in Europe. The yields are so high that it is hardly possible to enumerate them all. It is common for one seed to yield 10 to 20 times its amount, and sometimes even up to 50, which is well-documented by May. Often, a bushel of wheat has produced such returns.

There may be all kinds of spices and vegetables, namely ginger, potatoes, artichokes, parsnips, carrots, parsley, and calamus, which grows abundantly wild. Melons, watermelons, cabbage, and all sorts of kitchen herbs could grow very well there. Hops grow naturally in the forest and can be planted with great advantage. Both flax and hemp can thrive exceedingly well, promising significant profit.

In addition to farmers being able to sustain themselves and even set something aside from working their land, landowners could also derive substantial annual income. This could be achieved by clearing the land, handing it over to a tenant who farms it with their labor, and providing seed for the first year's planting. As the farm develops and expands, the landowner takes half of the annual yield, managing the harvest and threshing with their workers. This arrangement yields substantial interest annually, often more than tenfold.

However, if the tenant leaves the land, they must properly sow and deliver it in good condition. Any deficiencies, whether from the land or other inventory, must be compensated to the landowner. If the tenant takes up the land at their own expense, cultivates it with the assistance and support of the landowner, and sows the first year with seed provided by the

landowner, they shall follow the same arrangement as mentioned before, adjusted according to the work and cultivation the tenant has accomplished.

They may also enjoy exemptions from certain charges for several years as provided by the landowner. If someone takes land at their own expense, cultivates it, sows or grazes it, they may enjoy freedom from charges for at least five years. With this in place, others could cultivate the land, which would lead to significant income and profit for the landowners. Much of the population would be maintained by this, and the tenants would be exempt from taxes.

There is a much greater benefit from tobacco plantations, where each tenant is required to plant and tend to 2,500 to 3,000 tobacco plants, the yield from which can not only support the worker's basic living needs, but also provide a significant surplus for other purposes. The aforementioned number of tobacco plants yield 375 to 450 florins annually over 6 years. From this, wages, drinks, and medical costs are deducted and a worker receives half the remainder. Passengers over the age of eight brought over must give 50 florins for freight and provisioning, which amounts to 20 riksdaler. Those who cannot pay will be given work for 3 years, with their food and clothing provided in return.

2. There is also a considerable profit to be made from the forest, as the whole land is overrun with it; from oaks, hazel, hard aspen, etc. which could be used for timber, beams, planks, wagon wheels, roof tiles, pipestaves as well as quivers, beautiful cupboards and chests, fishing rods, fine pistol stocks, and saffras for medicine and other uses.

Fruit-bearing trees, besides the aforementioned walnut trees (both white and black), chestnut, mulberry, plum trees, apple trees, cherry trees, apricots, peaches, plums, almonds, laurel, and other fruit trees could be planted. They would thrive well and bear fruit and the potential profit from such planting can be easily apparent to any reasonable person.

Vineyards can also be established there, as the land supports four types of wine vines, although the grapes need to be dried

properly to be of good quality. Spanish, Rhineland and French vines would all thrive there and provide significant profit.

From timber and planks, as well as all other woodworking, there is a significant profit to be made, especially for export to the Caribbean, where such manufactures can be sold for either money or even tobacco. Additionally, there are waterways that are ideal for setting up sawmills, where the timber can be transported to make planks, boards, and whatever else is desired.

3. From livestock, there is a great profit to be gained, such as from oxen, cows, horses, cattle, pigs, sheep, goats, hens etc. In Virginia, a cow sells for 50 florins, and we could profit greatly from trade in cattle with that colony. An arrangement could be made whereby tenants receive a cow, in return for which he provides a portion of the butter and other produce.

Horses can also be kept, as well as other livestock such as goats, pigs, chickens, and cows, all for good profit. The pastureland is beyond measure, all good land, except for that near the river, which is low-lying.

4. The hunting in this land is moderately good, as it is wild and abundant with game, particularly deer, elk, rabbits, bears, wolves, lynxes, foxes, martens and minks. Otters and beavers are found in small numbers along the river, but many nations of the Minquas²⁰, both white and black, as well as other native groups, live many miles into the interior of the land.

Beaver skins are the most marketable goods there, and are like currency in all purchases, costing 9 fl. or 3 Riksdalers and 10 stuivers. These are significant in the food and clothing trade and could earn up to 1000 Riksdalers annually. There would be no need for any middlemen, otherwise, we would be constantly poor. However, the Dutch could annually bring 15,000 to 16,000 beaver pelts from the North River, apart from other pelts, generating an annual income of 128,000 florins.

²⁰ Susquehannock.

There is an abundance of waterfowl on the river and creeks. Wild geese are especially numerous. The white-headed geese arrive in late March and stay for 14 days before departing. Then the speckled geese arrive and remain for another 14 days before heading north. In the autumn, the gray geese return from the north and travel south in large flocks with loud calls. There are also swans and cranes, both large and small, as well as sandpipers and shorebirds. These can be caught with snares, nets, or hooks. They provide a great supply of meat for food and feathers for bedding and other uses.

5. Fisheries can also bring remarkable profit, as both in autumn and spring, and partly in summer, one can use nets, hooks, fish traps, and other fishing tools. The rivers and creeks are so abundant with fish that the catch, when salted or smoked, could not only feed the population but also sustain a significant trade. At the Great Falls near Fort Christina, large numbers of salmon are caught, which the Dutch call [irrewelf?]. This fish is smoked much like herring. Other large fish such as eels, perch and bream are plentiful in the rivers, as well sturgeon, which can be used to produce oil and preserved in barrels as they do in Elblag, Danzig and Hamburg. The English consider sturgeon an excellent delicacy. This could provide substantial profit, along with oysters found in the harbours and creeks. These oysters, of excellent quality, lie in large banks along with sea-spiders²¹ and turtles.

In the bay and beyond we could catch cod, mackerel and other sea fish, which would bring in a fine profit. The English and French usually make from such fishing on the Newfoundland banks 50-60,000 pounds sterling annually, with many shiploads being brought to Europe, to Portugal and beyond. Whales occasionally enter the bay, and although they are not often seen by men, it is not impossible and highly profitable if they are caught.

6. It is clear that various metals and minerals can be found there, such as saltpetre in the soil, sulphur, precious earths, ochre, red clay, white clay suitable for pottery, and blue clay valuable for

²¹ This is unlikely to refer to the modern-day order of Pantopoda known as sea spiders, most likely an edible crustacean like a shrimp or shellfish.

tiles and pottery. Skilled craftsmen and useful artisans could also be employed here.

7. Many tradespeople could be established in the country who could craft goods from the materials found there, supporting themselves and generating notable profits. These include tanners to process the many elk and deer hides, which are costly goods both locally and in Europe. Linen weavers could produce linen and cloth, which are valuable and in demand everywhere. Rope-makers could create ropes and cords for ships and fishing gear. Carpenters, sawyers, turners, coopers, and joiners could make furniture, chests, and barrels. Fishermen and fowlers could supply food. Brewers, bakers, blacksmiths, locksmiths, miners, sulphur burners, gunpowder makers, brickmakers, potters, lime burners, tar distillers, and others could establish themselves here. This would populate and develop the country, ensuring the livelihood of the people and securing a good income for the proprietors.
8. Finally, trade through seafaring would greatly advance and enhance all these means of development for the country's prosperity, provided it is organized properly and conducted efficiently. It is clear that trade and shipping there, with God's help, could flourish as follows:

(1) Regular shipping between Sweden and New Sweden must always be maintained, ensuring that the cargo sent from Sweden is well disposed of, and the ships promptly return with goods without unnecessary delay. Competent men, fluent in the local language and skilled in selling goods like pelts and other wares, are essential.

Many of the goods that they have for trade there, such as linen, flax, cloth, iron, steel, copper kettles, various mills, hoes, pickaxes, as well as shoes, socks, can be exchanged for tobacco, partly also for goods like fabrics from St. Christopher, tobacco, indigo, or silver coins, where loyal and trustworthy factors must be established. Fine bread, good ale, brandy, wine, and whiskey can best be exchanged in Virginia.

(2) As for the goods that could be produced in New Sweden, such as bread, ale, butter, meat, salted pork, fish, preserved fish,

timber, and wooden manufactures, these could be sent to Virginia and exchanged for tobacco. Likewise: moose hides, deer skins, beaver pelts, and furs could be exchanged in with New England. Tobacco, fine wood, cypress, hazel, sassafras, calamus, etc., and more goods that produced there, could be sent back home in return shipments. Additionally, pipe-staves and other timber could be sent on the return journey to Portugal and Algeria, where, after two or three winters, one barrel of wine could be obtained, which would be brought back home and sold, thereby making a profit from freight and travel expenses.

In this way, trade between New Sweden and the homeland could be strengthened and expanded, potentially generating considerable revenue. With sufficient capital, it could even yield gold in the future, benefiting the Crown and the Swedish nation, as other nations have profited from their colonial ventures.

Colonies

The more that are established there, the better they are found to be. The English trade from their colonies in America is estimated to bring in many thousands of pounds sterling annually, not to mention the conquest of the beautiful lands they possess there. The French trade from New France used to amount annually to 60 to 70 thousand livres before the English took their most prominent fortresses in New France from them in 1654. The Dutch trade in the North River has grown to 70 to 80 boats annually, not even counting the fur trade. They also purchase tobacco from the Virginians, where 12 to 16 large cargo ships receive freight every year. In the South River and New Sweden, there were previously many hundreds of boats, in addition to many other furs traded, but now trade has greatly diminished there. However, if this endeavor were restored with strong capital and power, it could once again become what it was, and trade could be revived.

Four impartial considerations are submitted concerning the repair of the damages and injustices inflicted upon us Swedes by the Dutch:

1. That an impartial commission be established over this matter, to examine the documents proving our rightful claim to the land, evidence of Dutch attacks, accounts of capital, expenses, compensation for damages, and interest, both for the whole company and for private individuals who have served it, so that everything can be reviewed, discussed, and resolved.
2. That, according to His Majesty's directive and decision, our rightful claim to the entirety of New Sweden's river be firmly pursued with the States-General of the Netherlands, and that their attacks, damages, and affronts be strongly protested, so that they are brought to reason. Should it be deemed proper for them to relinquish the land entirely, they must be well compensated with proper restitution, and if settlements have already been established there, then compensation must include interest, damages, and concessions. It also seems beneficial that, if we come to terms with them, our firm protest could compel them to fully pay reparations and grant us favorable conditions to continue alongside their colonies, with all freedom and undisturbed ability to manage our work and trade, which appears to be the most advisable course.
3. To the same end, satisfaction should be demanded from the King of Spain regarding the matter of the Kattan that was wrecked at Puerto Rico in 1649, the artillery and goods of which were seized and the crew mistreated, even though peace had already been established with them as well as with the treaty signed in Münster. However, upon the protest and authorization of Her Royal Majesty Queen Christina, the agent Hendrik von Elswick in 1654 received assurances of compensation for the ship and goods from the then-Governor of Puerto Rico, which amounted to 44,000 Riksdaler, and also obtained letters for the Spanish authorities, which he still holds in his possession. It may therefore happen that, if this claim is pursued at the proper time and with due demand, the matter will be successfully settled.

The following measures should be taken to sustain the colonies: (1) Securing the aforementioned payment from Spain. (2) Obtaining restitution from the Dutch. (3) Granting free privileges to

individuals or companies willing to establish colonies, including titles such as counties or lordships, under agreements either collective or personal. (4) The necessary governance should be set up both domestically and abroad to maintain order, ensuring monopolists do not take undue advantage. (5) All who invest in the company should enjoy privileges without exception.

Vol. 196, ff.288r-
307r. Swedish.

34. RISINGH'S PROPOSALS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF
NEW SWEDEN

To her Royal Majesty,

There are several ports where ships can come and go when Stockholm is frozen, namely places like Gothenburg, Wismar, Bremen, and Slite (Gotland), etc., where they are allowed and quays permit loading etc., where others participate and engage in commerce and where related affairs are set in proper order, so that ships, when their allotted times have passed, can depart and others can arrive, no time being wasted or delays caused.

This is how the other colonial powers in America operate: the Portuguese, the English for example, departing and arriving in the East and West Indies at scheduled times. New Sweden is really not so distant from Sweden as might seem, provided one maintains the correct course westwards. Swedish ships have been able to sail from New Sweden all the way to Öresund in 30 days. Therefore, it is ordered that ships take the shortest route and avoid the Caribbean Sea unless absolutely necessary, as it lies many miles off course. Instead, they should sail farther northward, as this route is both faster and cooler, reducing the crew's suffering from heat and the slowness of the journey. This allows the voyage to be completed more quickly and under better conditions for the crew's health.

People should not hesitate to settle in New Sweden, as the land is otherwise proven to be a temperate and pleasant place, with neither excessively hot summers nor overly cold winters. Who would not be able to endure such a climate? It would not only be advantageous for the land's prosperity, but the inhabitants could sustain themselves as well as other nations do. This will become evident through experience, as the region is suitable for clearing land, establishing plantations, farming and raising livestock, along

with fishing, hunting, and trade with the Indians. Our nation should yield to no other in this respect. As for trade with Christians there, namely the English and Dutch, it is true we are not yet as experienced or advanced as might be desired. However, with time and practice, our colonists will learn to conduct commerce just as well as others and sustain themselves accordingly. This would bring wealth to the region and prove to be more profitable in the long run than trading in Europe.

The second objection to the continuation of these colonies is that, at this time, only a small amount of capital can be raised for such an important endeavour, which requires significant investment by some power or benefactor, as the English have provided for their colonies. However, in contrast, it has been found in Sweden that there is a very limited tax base, even though a special tax was levied on the entire kingdom for this purpose.

Previously, a significant and notable contribution was made in Sweden during the time of Gustav Adolf of blessed memory, when funds were successfully collected. At that time, such projects and intentions would have achieved success had it not been for the difficult wars and other obstacles that interfered. From this, it is evident that the lack of resources is not the true hindrance but rather that the work has not been driven with sufficient focus and determination. Therefore, the goal remains feasible, and although this plan has so far been delayed, it may still achieve success in the future provided that it is pursued with capable management and focused effort.

And how many times have the English been obstructed in such efforts, when their entire possessions in Bermuda and other places in America were lost? Yet they did not abandon their plans but continued to establish their colonies, so that now they have well-cultivated provinces and wealthy lands from which they conduct significant and profitable commerce.

It is objected, however, that now is a most unsuitable time to speak of colonies, shipping, and the advancement of commerce, as the kingdom is so burdened by war on all sides and the estates are scarcely able to raise the funds needed for the costs of defense. Indeed, it is uncertain when circumstances will allow us to expect peace.

It is certainly true that the kingdom, burdened by so many obligations, heavily oppresses the fatherland, so that His Majesty's subjects can bear no more. Nevertheless, it is no less appropriate to have thoughts of peace and peaceful endeavors even in the midst of war, just as in the deepest peace one must still consider matters of war. For such projects, which aim to alleviate the heavy burden brought by war, point to ways in which resources can be obtained during such difficulties for His Majesty's benefit, the improvement of the treasury, and the prosperity and advancement of his subjects. And although such efforts are often hindered by pressing hardships, the plan still remains both good and entirely feasible to implement, for not all difficult and burdensome matters are immediately impossible.

The Dutch have demonstrated this courageously, for example, during the most difficult war against the Spaniards, during which they nonetheless established colonies in both the East and West Indies. Through this, they gained renown for their diligence, acquired resources despite their poverty, and with these means made their powerful kingdom capable of such strong resistance, inflicting notable setbacks on their enemies. Are we to believe that the Dutch alone are capable of such things?

A counterargument, raised by the English, is based on their prior claim to the rights of the river where New Sweden is located. Specifically, they assert that they were the first to explore this region, particularly through Sebastian Cabot, who in the year 1496 discovered the coasts of America, from the 67th degree of latitude north all the way to Florida at the 90th (sic) degree. All of this was undertaken on the commission and command of King Henry VII, during which our river (Delaware) is also said to have been discovered.

Lord Baltimore has, through King James's donation, obtained all the land located between Virginia and the 40th degree of latitude, a claim in which our river is situated. Sir Edmund Plowden claims rights as well, not through the aforementioned donation but rather based on a large sum and expenses he incurred during a voyage he undertook around the year 1646. He was detained by the Swedish governor, Johan Printz, and his goods were confiscated.

He made it known to me in conversation that he intended to send his son there with a group of people to take possession of the river. Furthermore, the English residing in New Haven and New England also claim many tracts of land in the aforementioned river, which they say they have purchased, and their colonies have even employed some of our servants. They have often written to us about this matter and were ready on several occasions to take action to establish their colonies there, particularly in the year 1655. However, through good mediation, these efforts were prevented.

Answer: As for the English claim based on their discovery, the matter stands as follows: if the mere discovery of a land were sufficient to establish rightful ownership, then others would have a better claim to it, as they discovered the region, including the forests and the river, long before the English. It is not reasonable that one should gain ownership simply because they set foot in a place or happen to come upon it. However, if one acquires ownership through some legitimate transaction and establishes possession, then that party is the rightful owner. If a person owns the land and does not abandon or relinquish it, they cannot lose their right simply because another party enters or intervenes.

Baltimore and Plowden thus claim the aforementioned river based on donations from Kings James and Charles. These donations hold no more weight, being of similar value to the Pope's donation, through which he freely granted and assigned to the King of Castile all of the West Indies, along with whatever lay westward of the prime meridian, and to the King of Portugal, the Indies and all the lands located east of that line.

But the Pope granted what he neither owned nor had the right to give, and thus such a grant is of no value. This has been clearly demonstrated by the English themselves, as well as by the French, Dutch, and other nations, through their actions. Despite the Pope's donation, they have occupied and taken possession of the same lands in both the East and West Indies that the Pope had ostensibly granted to the Spaniards and Portuguese. Thus, the Pope's donation has no weight, and the same can be said of the grants made by King James. The claims derived from those grants are just as weak as those of Lord Baltimore and Sir Edmund Plowden, who have no legitimate ownership or possession of the aforementioned land, as they had not actually taken possession of

it before our colony. Our colony acquired the land properly through purchase from the Indians, the rightful owners, and has since taken possession of it.

To clarify this matter, legitimate claims to ownership of lands are based on: occupation, taking possession of unoccupied lands, through just war, the acquisition of territory through legitimate conflict or through lawful agreement, either through a rightful peace treaty or other rightful means of acquisition.

The granting of property requires the rightful owner to make the gift. It is futile to bestow something that one does not own. The donor must have legitimate ownership, and the recipient must take possession and occupy it; otherwise, the gift is forfeited. Now, the English neither had rightful ownership of the lands of the Indians nor authority over them. Instead, they claim to have received this land as a grant from King James, who had no legitimate claim to it. Moreover, they had not even taken possession of the said river or the lands before our colony had already inhabited it.

Without purchase from a rightful owner and the taking into actual possession, any claim to title may be lost and rendered void. The English have thus no just title, while we Swedes possess this river, having made use of it. From the rightful owners, we have acquired these titles either through gifts or purchases, obtaining them from the mouth of the river all the way to the falls. We have received and established these rights and have taken full possession of the land.

Regarding the claims of the settlers from New England, it is known that those from New Haven purchased some tracts of land along the river. However, this was done under dubious circumstances, as the Swedes had already established ownership and possession of most of the river, supported by documentation and lawful claims. Despite their assertions, the English have no rightful claim to these lands, nor do the Native Americans have the right to grant land in the manner they claim.

While certain areas were previously bought, the settlers, though they may barter or act without legal authority, cannot assert any valid legal rights. Thus, the people of New Haven should have better understood the situation and not attempt to purchase land or make claims already rightfully held by the Swedes. For these

reasons, the English settlers must accept the Swede's rights to these lands and cease their attempts to settle there. Though many times they have tried to establish colonies on our river, they have been restrained by our magistrates and leaders, and there is no doubt that their claims lack any foundation.

It can be imagined that when the Swedish colony has established itself and expanded, both New Haveners and other English settlers could settle on their land and maintain good relations with us, providing they acknowledge our rights. But when settlers arrive, it is no use trying to drive them out, as they are already in possession.

Furthermore, the Dutch also want to lay claim to this river as their own, claiming that they were the first Christians to settle it, namely through Captain Hudson in the year 1609. At the time, under the auspices of the Dutch East India Company, he had sailed into the bay while seeking a western route to China and thus named this area, as it is still known today, namely Cape May and Henlopen. The Dutch, as they expanded, claimed our river for themselves. Afterwards, they purchased this territory from unwilling natives and later built settlements in this region, including Fort Nassau, located halfway up the river, and a house near the falls. Thus, they conclude that they hold rightful possession of the entire river and that the Swedes have no rights in the matter. Thus, they deem they have a right to continue expanding their colony here.

Answer: The Dutch or the West India Company's claim to these territories are of a similar nature and are of the same doubtful standing when it comes to ownership or acquisition. Even if they could present some claim to legitimacy, as has been proven, they cannot truly substantiate it. The English, however, base their claim on Sebastian Cabot having first explored the river (*An English Description of America*, London, 1655) and on the basis that Hudson had earlier sailed under a commission from King James I of England and not the Dutch. The latter nevertheless purchased maps from Hudson or his associates, of the areas discovered by him and named the area New Netherland. In 1614, they established their first colony on that river. The governor of Virginia, Samuel Argall, then claimed jurisdiction over them, and although they placed themselves under his authority for a time, they later received directives from Amsterdam, whereupon they

built settlements and forts, namely New Amsterdam (or Manhattan) and Fort Orange. They appointed their own governor and subsequently refused to pay contributions to the English.

Thus, King James of England's ambassador accused the States General of these actions. The Dutch excused themselves, claiming it was not a public enterprise but a private endeavour by the West India Company in Amsterdam. Consequently, Sir George Calvert, Lord Baltimore, was granted a commission to plant colonies above Virginia, now called Maryland, and Sir Edmund Plowden received authority to establish colonies in the northern parts of Virginia, where New Netherland is now located, up to New England, under one of the new estates called Albion. The Dutch then offered to withdraw, provided the English would pay them 2,500 pounds sterling, thereby resolving all claims they had in the area.

Dissent therefore arose and the Dutch served the wild Indians in a Christian manner with provisions and weapons to ensure their alliance with them, maintaining their presence in the country to this day. All of the documentation, however, shows that the Dutch have little legitimate claim by title, nor can they derive any benefit from the principle of possession because, while alleging that the entire river belongs to them by purchase, they can never provide proof that they actually bought it. Moreover, such a purchase cannot easily be made, as no single owner exists over all whole river; rather, each distinct tract belongs to specific owners. The land properly belongs to each indigenous group and its sachem.

The Dutch have not purchased the extent of land they claim, as their own deeds will show. Although the Dutch have bought some tracts along the river and established houses or forts there, as previously mentioned, this does not prejudice the Swedes' rights in the river. According to what I have heard, those Dutch who were established on our river abandoned the project and transferred it to us Swedes, a matter well-known to our gracious government, who have acted with proper authorization. Since the Dutch West India Company's successes in Brazil in 1629 and the following years, with their significant profits from silver mines, etc. they have shifted their priorities away from northern ventures. Thus, the Dutch have been more focused on their trade

and private commercial expectations than on territorial claims in this region.

Several burghers of Amsterdam were granted territories, namely Samuel Goddin, who was given authority over the western side of our river while Albert Coenraadsz Burgh was assigned the eastern side of the bay. Samuel Blomart received the [Canitocot or Fish River?], along with islands, namely Barbados and St. Martin, which the English now possess. The fourth proprietor was Kiliaen van Rensselaer, who was to establish his colony in the North River area. He placed his colony near Fort Orange in a region called Rensselaerwijck, where he reportedly brought 10 to 50 families to settle.

The area to the west of the bay (allocated to Samuel Goddin), became a colony, but its settlers faced constant disturbances from the native population. Despite attempts to maintain relations with the Indigenous people, the area was plagued by unrest. Subsequently, the directors of the West India Company, including Samuel Blomart, Albert Conradus, and others, made arrangements with Minuit, a former servant of the Dutch West India Company. Minuit, under the Swedish Crown, initiated actions in the South River region in 1651, purchasing various lands along the river and establishing Fort Christina near the Minquas. He called the area New Sweden.

Later, Johan Printz was sent as governor with ships full of settlers to expand the colony. These efforts secured Sweden's claims to the land and the river, forcing the Dutch to retreat. Had the colony been supported by reinforcements and resources, it could have been more effectively maintained. Under such circumstances, the river and the surrounding land would have remained firmly under Swedish control, with both English and Dutch claims over the region definitively nullified.

Thus, the Swedes have as much right to the land and the river as the others, having acquired it through legitimate purchase from its rightful native owners. The Swedes took actual possession of significant parts of the land, leaving the Dutch with no stronger claim. Any further assertions by the Dutch would not be founded on justice or legitimate warfare but rather resemble acts of privateering or piracy. We have suffered this unjust attack upon

our rightful possessions, and seek redress from God and our sovereign for these grievances.

Lastly, there is much doubt and debate about whether any profit or benefit can be expected from this colony, considering the significant expenses already incurred and the many lives that have been risked in its establishment. The advantages which the Kingdom of Sweden and its subjects might derive from establishing a proper colony in America, are therefore:

Since the land is so conveniently located, so vast and so fertile, many families could be accommodated there. Not only could many impoverished people sustain themselves but more prosperous families could also provide their children with opportunities in shipping and trade, which they otherwise could not afford due to a lack of means. Many disbanded soldiers and other servitors could also be rewarded with lands. This would generate revenue in turn the defense and maintenance of the realm. In particular, an active shipping and trade relationship between the kingdom and the colonies could greatly support this.

The land called New Sweden in America, lies approximately between the 39th and 40th lines of latitude. It is a region that aligns well with our nation's climate. It is situated along a great river, which the English call the Delaware and the Dutch the South River, and it is considered one of the best areas in North America. The river itself is navigable for 30 miles and there are numerous creeks, fourteen of which are navigable. These waterways abound with fish, and they could support several hundred families. This river and its surroundings could serve as an excellent harbor for various ships traveling north or south along the coast, making it convenient for ships to restock water, repair masts, or obtain other goods that could be produced locally. This would provide an opportunity to establish sustainable commerce in the region.

In addition to its many natural advantages, the land's soil is particularly fertile, especially on the western bank of the river. It is well-suited for growing various European crops and sustaining livestock without much difficulty. This means that not only could the colonists comfortably sustain themselves, but they could also produce enough provisions to supply ships and even export to other places. Because of these qualities, the land could

significantly benefit both the homeland and the governing authorities, as well as the settlers themselves. The area holds great potential for economic development through several key industries: fisheries, hunting, agriculture, raising livestock, brewing, milling, manufacturing and, ultimately, trade and shipping.

It would be possible to establish productive fishing operations here. A significant portion of the company's workforce could be employed in these endeavors at the falls near Christina, where we could catch a substantial amount of fish that are otherwise hard to obtain such as herring, goby, eels, and other species. A large number of sturgeon can also be caught and preserved as done in Gdansk and Hamburg, which is a much sought-after delicacy, especially among the English. Substantial profits could therefore be made from it.

In the bay and surrounding waters, one could catch a large quantity of cod and other marine species. Although it might not yield as much as the English and French gain from their fisheries near Newfoundland, which are estimated to bring in up to 50,000 pounds sterling annually, there is still potential. Whaling, while presently not particularly abundant or well-established in the area, could also be developed over time, with patience and proper effort. There are good oysters in the bays and estuaries, clustered together in large beds. These could be harvested both in these locations and transported to other places, providing a reliable source of food and trade.

Hunting and fur-trading are excellent here, as the forests are rich in game, such as deer, moose, hare, rabbits, bears, wolves, foxes, mink and West Indian martens that could be hunted. Beavers and otters are somewhat rarer in this area but still present. Most valuable, however, are the white pelts or furs which are brought in by the white Minquas, the black Minquas²², the [Benequeser?], the [Magoeker?] and other indigenous peoples who live about 100 miles inland. These pelts are the most common merchandise in the region and are often used as currency. This trade is not inconsiderable, providing as it does sustenance, goods, and

²² Johnson pp.188-191 speculates on these. The white Minquas were most likely the Susquehannock, an Iroquoian people distinct from the Lenape who predominated along the Delaware. The identity of the 'black Minquas' is more uncertain but likely a closely-related group.

opportunities for commerce with high demand for these furs and their associated products.

The forests are abundant with birds, including partridges and pigeons in great flocks, as well as eagles, cormorants and various bigger and heavier birds of prey. The river and the creeks are also teeming with birds, namely various species of wild geese, including black geese, which arrive in March. Among them are white-headed geese, which remain for about a fortnight. After that, flocks of mottled geese appear. During this time, they begin to head northward, suggesting that there must be some body of water there where they gather. When they arrive and move on again, they flock in unbelievably-vast numbers. There are also cranes, herons, snipes, sandpipers and other smaller birds, all of which can be hunted, netted, or trapped. This abundance of birds could yield significant profit, both as food and from their feathers, which could be used for bedding and clothing.

There is great potential in agriculture and the soil here is capable of improvement so that various crops could be grown, for example: maize, rye, barley, wheat, and peas, not to mention various roots and vegetables, such as ginger, artichokes, parsnips, carrots, parsley, calamus, melons, persimmons, and all sorts of cabbage and garden plants. Hops were also found growing in the forests, which could be transplanted into hopyards. Flax and hemp also grew well there and could soon be cultivated successfully, providing a great profit.

Apart from the fact that everyone who worked the land could sustain themselves and fertilise it, the company could also derive great profits from it, provided that the company cleared the land and ensured that good men were given plots and, during the first years, removed stumps and burned the undergrowth to clear the land.

And thereafter, the annual yield would be harvested with shared effort and expenses, divided so that the company gets half and the cultivators the other half. The harvest would then be stored and threshed, with each party taking their share, and half of that portion would be set aside as seed for the following year, allowing the cycle to continue year after year.

The land that the tenant wished to vacate would remain his responsibility, and he would have the right to sell his property,

ensuring it was left in good condition. Plows and other equipment would become the company's property, and should anything be damaged due to his negligence, he would be liable for it. In this way, the land could remain productive without imposing significant expenses on the company, with 100 dalers' worth of tobacco from the small parcel being considered a modest return.

If anyone wished to cultivate the Company's land with his own people and labour, and desired to settle there, he could be provided with seed grain and land under the condition that in the following year, he would yield the entire harvest, and thereafter, as long as he continued to hold the land, he would deliver a portion of the annual yield from the land—one-sixth, one-eighth, one-ninth, or one-tenth, depending on what was previously agreed upon. Through these and other measures, the land could be cleared, cultivated, and developed, reducing costs for the Company while allowing settlers to live exempt from taxes.

There is, furthermore, great potential benefit to be derived from tobacco plantations, with which this land could really fulfil its potential. All colonists could be obliged by the Company to cultivate 2,000 to 3,000 tobacco plants, which would yield 3,000 to 4,000 pounds of tobacco and a great profit. This calculation does not include the costs for horses etc., which would not be excessively high. Each worker would be expected to serve for at least three years, covering the costs of transport and the Company's expenses, would amount to 40 to 50 florins per worker or approximately 16 to 20 Riksdaler.

This endeavour could progress significantly with proper management and supervision. A large number of labourers could be put to work, overseen by one or two capable foremen, who would lead the operations, ensure the proper handling of the tobacco, and see to its correct processing.

There would be no small advantage in the colony from acquiring livestock, both large and small, namely cows, sheep, goats, or horses. In Virginia, a cow can be purchased for 40 to 60 florins, whereas in the South River, the same cow costs 100 to 130 florins. If the Company were to purchase a livestock there, it would yield a significant profit. Similarly, if the Company could procure horses, reports from Virginia suggest that three calving cows have

been offered in exchange for a single horse. If one were to lease or lend cows, this too would not be without benefit, as for each cow, all the milk for the year and then half of the offspring would belong to the Company.

The aforementioned agricultural activities producing good grain, brewing, milling, and baking would consequently generate considerable profit for the company. Grain could be ground into flour, as there are excellent locations by streams suitable for mills. The flour could either be shipped in barrels or baked into hard bread that preserves well. One could also establish malt houses, where good quantities of barley could be malted and then brewed into fine beer or distilled into spirits. These products, such as beer and brandy, are highly sought after in Virginia and the Caribbean islands. Moreover, they could yield a good profit, along with tobacco and other trade goods that could be exchanged.

There is a significant profit to be made from forestry and timber. The whole land is abundant with fine trees, both black and white [?]. Toward the eastern regions, there are vast pine forests, from which planks, beams, and all kinds of timber products could be produced. The convenient locations near the streams allow for the establishment of sawmills, where such timber can be processed and cut as desired. Additionally, the dark wood of certain trees resembles ebony, and with skillful craftsmanship, it can be worked into high-quality products.

There are many other types of trees which would grow well in this country, namely chestnut, walnut, black and white mulberry trees, mistletoe, plum, and apple trees, peach, apricot, cherry, fig, almond, laurel and other fruitful trees that could be transplanted from abroad. Vineyards could be established here, as wild grapes grow in many places, although the latter are not particularly suitable for pressing into wine. Still, there is interest in trying Spanish or French varieties, as the climate here may be suitable for such grapevines.

Numerous handicrafts could also be established in the country, depending on the materials available there, which could be processed and manufactured to generate significant profit. For example, cobblers, of whom there are many, and whose products are highly valued both locally and in Europe, would be useful. Linen and textiles are always in demand out in the colonies,

ropemakers for ships' rigging, yarn and material for fishing tackle. There would also be opportunities for sawyers, woodturners, coopers, carpenters—both small and large scale—fishermen, bird catchers, brewers, bakers, and mineral specialists to look for [O:D?²³] and other minerals, which surely exist in large quantities. Sulphur refineries and gunpowder mills could also be established, as brimstone is found there. There is also no shortage of fine clay available—red, white, blue, etc.—that could be of use. Additionally, lime kilns using oyster shells, tar distilleries from pine, and other such works could be established, which would help attract work and therefore settlers to the land. Skilled trades such as tailors, shoemakers, and others could find work and contribute to the production of quality goods. The country's and the Company's great profit would increase accordingly. Furthermore, shipbuilding could be established, as there is an abundant supply of oak timber available. This would not only allow the building of ships and vessels for domestic use but also for sale to others, providing livelihoods and sustenance for many people.

As for what has been mentioned earlier regarding the development of the land, it could, in my opinion (with God's blessing), grow and be improved further if trade and commerce were properly organized and established on the right course, which seems to me the best way forward. Regarding the cargo that is brought to Sweden or Europe, it should be carefully managed to ensure that the ships are quickly unloaded and return without unnecessary delays. As for the goods useful to the Christian population there, they include linen, hemp, wool, cloth, needles, thread, yarn, silk, iron tools, shirts, shoes, stockings, etc.

Bread, beer, wine and spirits could be sold in Virginia, St. Christopher, and other Caribbean islands to great profit. For this, one can obtain sugar or silver in payment, provided that good and trustworthy factors and merchants are stationed there. Goods that are prepared or available in the country could also be sent to other nearby lands and islands. The same is true for other items of agricultural produce, fruit, wooden manufactured products, cheese, butter and meat, which could all be exported to the Caribbean. Hides, both tanned and untanned, along with other leather goods, may be sent to New England. Beer, bread, wine,

²³ Obsidian is possibly intended here.

and brandy can also be traded in Virginia and the islands, along with timber, planks, and other raw materials, as well as iron and steel, which are useful there. Tobacco, sugar, silver and other commodities can be obtained in return for these. Items not produced locally could be imported and ships could also carry timber and pipe staves to Portugal and the Algarve, where they can often be exchanged for wine or other goods.

Thus, the West Indian trade could be firmly established between the fatherland and the colonies. Within a short time, it would yield substantial wealth, enriching Sweden and strengthening the Swedish nation, just as other nations have benefited from their colonies. The English estimate their trade to and from their colonies in the West Indies at several hundred thousand pounds sterling annually, not including what they have gathered through conquest, from which their homeland receives significant support, which we could likewise benefit from.

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| Vol. 196, ff.309r-326v. Swedish. | 35. | LATER COPY OF THE PRECEDING DOCUMENT

Handwriting changes f.315r. |
| Vol. 196, f.330r. Dutch. | 36. | INVENTORY OF GOODS DELIVERED TO JOAN BORT AND CAPTAIN BAERENT HARMAN. |
| Vol. 196, f.332r. Swedish. | 37. | INVENTORY OF THE TYPES OF AMMUNITION REQUIRED FOR NEW SWEDEN, WHAT ARRANGEMENTS HAVE BEEN MADE FOR THE EXISTING SUPPLIES, AS WELL AS WHAT IS LACKING |
| Vol. 196, f.333r. Swedish. | 38. | INVENTORY OF AMMUNITION AND MATERIEL THAT HAS YET TO BE DELIVERED FROM THE ROYAL WAR COLLEGE AS ORDERED IN HER ROYAL MAJESTY'S INSTRUCTIONS |

On land:

- 2 eight-pound iron cannons
- 4 six-pound iron cannons
- 4 four-pound iron cannons
- Additionally, two twelve-pound cannons made of metal

Cannons for the new ship:

- 4 six-pound iron cannons
- 4 four-pound iron cannons
- 4 three-pound iron cannons
- 2 two-pound iron cannons
- Additionally, 6 Russian cartridge papers along with the required

powder charges, wadding, and fuses.

- 2-pound cannonballs: 400
- 8-pound cannonballs: 400
- 4-pound cannonballs: 1,000
- 2-pound cannonballs: 300
- 1-pound cannonballs: 200

Gunpowder:

- 1 load of gunpowder
- 1 barrel of good gunpowder for the militia
- 1 bellows apparatus